

Mixed-Component Signal Transduction Systems: The Debate over the Classification of Potential RNA-Protein Complex-based Gas-Sensing Biomolecules

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Running title: Mixed-Component Signal Transduction Systems

Keywords: cell signaling, gasocrine signaling, signal transduction systems, receptor, gasoreceptor, gaseous signaling molecule, gasocrinology

In the emerging field of gasocrinology, identifying all the biomolecules that directly perform the gas-sensing role is essential.¹ Most research has focused on protein-based receptors, or gasoreceptors, and proteins that require gases as substrates for its enzymatic activity, or sensors.²⁻⁴ However, I recently proposed the possibility of RNA- and DNA-based receptors, or riboreceptors and deoxyriboceptors, respectively, for various classes of molecules and factors, including gases.^{5,6}

A protein with sensing and signaling domains in different regions functions as a one-component signal transduction system.⁷ I also proposed that proteins with overlapping sensing and signaling domains can function as a proto-component signal transduction system⁸, whereas a protein complexes consisting of at least two proteins - one performing a sensing role and the other performing a signaling role - can function as split-component signal transduction systems.⁹ Based on these models, catalytic nucleic acids in which a single region performs both sensing and signaling functions can be considered to act as a proto-component signal transduction system. Conversely, catalytic nucleic acids with two different regions for sensing and signaling can be considered one-component signal transduction systems. Finally, catalytic nucleic acids that form a complex with another nucleic acid performing the sensing role can be considered to act in a split-component signal transduction system.

However, nucleic acids are not always found in isolation within a cell. They interact with other nucleic acids, proteins, other biomolecules and factors.¹⁰ If such nucleic acid-protein complexes perform a sensing role, and if sensing and signaling are performed by either protein or RNA, or vice versa, the question arises: How should such a signal transduction system be classified? Whether RNA-protein complexes that perform the sensing and signaling roles can be classified as a receptor or riboreceptor in a mixed-component signal transduction system remains a topic of debate.

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